

**PROVOCĂRILE TERMINOLOGIEI ȘI TRANSFERULUI CONCEPTUAL
ÎN DISCURSUL REGELUI FILIP AL VI-LEA AL SPANIEI:
O PERSPECTIVĂ PRAGMATICĂ /**

**THE CHALLENGES OF TERMINOLOGY AND CONCEPTUAL TRANSFER
IN THE DISCOURSE OF KING FELIPE VI OF SPAIN:
A PRAGMATIC PERSPECTIVE**

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This presentation explores the challenges of terminology and conceptual transfer in the discourse of King Felipe VI, focusing on diplomatic ceremonial contexts. From a pragmatic perspective, royal discourse is shaped by culturally embedded values, institutional roles and historical community. Translating or analyzing such discourse involves navigating terms with no direct equivalents and concepts tied to national identity, tradition, or constitutional monarchy. We examine how politeness, strategies, deixis and implicit meaning require careful interpretation. These elements pose challenges not only for translation, but also for ensuring the speakers intended image and authority are accurately conveyed across languages and cultures.